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Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem

Cross-Cutting Activity #1

Support to the generation and the development of start-ups and spin-offs

Deliverable DCC1.1 – March 2023
Report on Activity plan and State of the art

i NEST

edited by ...

with the cooperation of:

....

Cover image: Piero Dorazio - Fenice obbediente, 1967

*The artist and the scientist, according to Dorazio, propose two different but parallel paths:
they broaden knowledge, working more for the future than for the present.*

*"I don't try to educate the viewer about the function of color,
but rather to complete my own education on its possibilities."*

(from "Piero Dorazio" by Maurizio Fagiolo dell'Arco - Officina Edizioni - Roma, 1966).

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1 Abstract

The Cross Cutting Activity 1 of iNEST (CC1) project aims at boosting incubation and acceleration activities, contributing to the develop networks between Startupper, researcher, universities and SMEs in the Triveneto territory. The report will give full disclosure on the organizational model of the Ecosystem by highlighting the collaborative network and the guidelines for operational transparency.

The partners involved are then analyzed based on their support in each phase together with the global development strategy and the metrics necessary for understanding the future results of the cross-cutting activity. The report will also highlight the development results of the Key Standardized Elements on the pre-acceleration and the Key Centralized Elements on the acceleration. The report will also focus on the chronological transition from a decentralized yet coordinated SPOKES, with common standardized tools and guidelines, to a centralized acceleration hub.

University Partners

2 Introduction

This deliverable is dedicated to the ecosystem of acceleration for startups and researchers, an innovative initiative born from the collaboration of iNest universities with the goal of fostering entrepreneurial growth and scientific advancement.

Identification and analysis of successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-off among the INEST Project Partners. The purpose of this sub task is to map the project partners' initiatives and approaches aimed at turning research and technology development into business ideas. This is functional to the development of a framework for the project activities build around a common shared nucleus while retaining space for personalization to accommodate individual SPOKEs specificities.

In an era characterized by rapid technological evolution and the ever-increasing importance of innovation, universities are facing new challenges and opportunities in preparing the younger generation for a continuously transforming workforce. This report is the result of in-depth research and detailed analysis of the ecosystem of acceleration for startups and researchers involving into the iNest context. The analysis closely examines the context in which this acceleration ecosystem has emerged, the challenges it has faced, and the successes it has achieved in promoting innovation and collaboration among students, researchers, and industry professionals.

The universities involved in this initiative have recognized that startup acceleration and high-level scientific research are two sides of the same coin. By creating an environment that facilitates interaction and knowledge exchange between startups and researchers, innovative solutions for global challenges are stimulated, and the development of new entrepreneurial opportunities is fostered. This unique ecosystem is built upon the sharing of resources, expertise, and infrastructure among participating universities, enabling privileged access to a vast network of mentors, industry experts, investors, and business partners.

In this deliverable will be explored the key components of this acceleration ecosystem through the activities currently carried out by the partners involved. Will also be analyzed the training and mentoring programs offered to startups and researchers, as well as the dedicated innovation and prototyping facilities and laboratories. In conclusion this document will analyze the presence of funding strategies and targeted investments aimed to develop the growth and scalability of emerging startups.

Through interviews, case studies, and in-depth analysis, this document provides a comprehensive overview of how this acceleration ecosystem could bridge the gap between academic research and practical application, providing fertile ground for the emergence of successful projects and significant real-world impacts.

Creating a shared workplace, suitable for pre-investment trials

In other words, what is being proposed is a breakdown of barriers (including cultural ones) that prevent the worlds of research and production from communicating with each other. The projects outlined in the previous paragraph involve the creation of a true shared working environment for the players, an environment that also includes physical shared spaces. Such an environment is fundamental for the so-called “last mile”, the final step in the supply chain preceding the introduction of innovations to the market (Caccamo 2020, Doloreux 2023).

The first real step that can promote the creation of a shared work environment is the identification of issues of shared interest. In the lines of work expected by the iNEST, it will be necessary to find room for those spheres which the companies have recognized as being of particular interest. It is not redundant to underline that this interest on behalf of the companies is often driven by reasons far different from those of researchers in their chosen research goals. In other words, the trajectories of research and those of the market do not always correspond, with the first group being inspired by curiosity for knowledge and technological development, and the second group by concrete demands posed by potential customers, which can in fact be satisfied through the introduction of innovations. Moreover, this situation is furtherly complicated by the institutional side of the ecosystem: the governments may add other requirements (Etzkowitz 1997). For the actual attainment of the iNEST CCI goals, an alignment and verification phase with the institutions and the manufacturing world will be performed.

Preparing the research environment to support development of the region

Historically, it has always been thought that interaction between research and businesses takes place in a unidirectional manner, from the side that holds the knowledge (the research world) to the side that utilizes the know-how and takes it into the market (the companies). Plenty of evidence shows that this model was strongly weakened in the last decades by a series of factors, including global competition and reduction in public funding (De Wit-De Vries 2019).

What today appears as the best approach is a more articulated model, with reciprocal bidirectional exchange of knowledge between businesses and research, with a corporate role that is anything but marginal. In this model, researchers supply knowledge derived from trajectories of the international scientific community and mediates it with what the companies absorb from the market. It regards, therefore, a mechanism that involves even levels of contribution from the different players which enable non-linear processes but anticipate complex situations wherein the flow of information between sources is merged in a particular manner (Cai, 2020).

Thus, the goal is not only to put the companies in a condition to “receive” knowledge from scientific institutions, but also to enable reciprocal merging of knowledge, which allows the companies to learn from the research institutions and to the research institutions to learn from the market. Importantly, while global competition forces the companies (especially the larger players) to adopt innovation as mandatory for their survival, the risk of scarce permeability is stronger for the research side, which is often not motivated to interact with the territory (Qiu 2023).

One of the goals of iNEST CC1 is to guide research institutions to interact with the regional context, especially the entrepreneurial context, with the ultimate goal to contribute to regional development through continuous exchange and synergic interactions (Brekke 2021).

3 Planning of activities

Task CC1.1 - Planning and validation

Task Leader: UNIVE

Duration: M04 - M040

The purpose of this task is the planning of the activities of the cross-cutting activity CC1, the identification and analysis of the successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-off among the INEST Project Partners and the monitoring and validation of the results obtained. The task will be responsibility of a committee composed by the representatives of the SPOKEs. The members of the committee are:

Coordinator: Prof. Carlo Bagnoli, Ca' Foscari University of Venice, bagnoli@unive.it

Spoke 1: Prof. Francesco Ravazzolo, UNIBZ, francesco.ravazzolo@unibz.it

Spoke 2: Prof. Alessandro Rossi, UNITN, alessandro.rossi@unitn.it

Spoke 3: Prof. Piergiorgio Comuzzo, UNIUD piergiorgio.comuzzo@uniud.it

Spoke 4: Prof. Lorenzo Fabian, IUAV, lfabian@iuav.it

Spoke 5: Prof. Moreno Muffatto, UNIPD, moreno.muffatto@unipd.it

Spoke 6: Prof. Maria Lusiani, UNIVE, maria.lusiani@unive.it

Spoke 7: Prof. Diego Begalli, UNIVR, diego.begalli@univr.it

Spoke 8: Dott. Diego Santaliana, PTAA, diego.santaliana@poloaa.it

Spoke 9: Prof. Giovanni Noselli, SISSA, gnoselli@sisssa.it

The committee will be responsible of the overall supervision and direction of the CC1 activities and specifically will:

- Approve the appointment of the all the staff to be involved in the CC1 activities.
 - Decide the startups to be admitted to the acceleration phase taking into consideration of the advice given by a panel of sector experts and professional investors (i.e VCs).
 - Select the participating startups to be selected for the advancement through the project.
- Sub Task CC1.1.1: Planning of CC1 activities, in order to outline the approach or supporting the generation and the development of research start-ups and spin-offs and the project's partner contribution.

Responsible: UNIVE

Duration: months 4-7

- Sub Task CC1.1.2: Identification and analysis of successful practices of generation and development of research start-ups and spin-off among the INEST Project Partners. The purpose of this sub task is to map the project partners' initiatives and approaches aimed at turning research and technology development into business ideas. This is functional to the development of a framework for the project activities build around a common shared nucleus while retaining space for personalization to accommodate individual SPOKEs specificities.

Responsible: UNIVE.

Duration: months 4-8

- Sub Task CC1.1.3. Throughout the CC1 activities, the results data will be gathered and elaborated for assessing the success rates of the Innovation Ecosystem with a deep focus on its Pre Acceleration, Acceleration and Fundraising stages, in order to improve the innovation ecosystem's framework and support the progression of the same.

Responsible: UNIVE

Duration: months 5-40

- Sub Task CC1.1.4. Organization of co-innovation events and demo days. Direction of communication activities between the spokes and the hub with start-up/researcher and other ecosystem partners.

Responsible: IUAV

Duration: months 5-40

Task CC1.2 - Pre-acceleration

Task Leader: Unive

Duration: M09 - M40

The Pre-acceleration Phase will pursue 2 goals:

1. Scouting for researchers and early stage startups relevant for the general theme of the project and to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems.
2. Training in entrepreneurial skills of entrepreneurs-to-be.

To develop the decentralized pre-acceleration phase, a number of Key Standardized Elements will be developed, to promote consistent and coordinated actions, methodologies, and results. The Key Standardized Elements are: a) a Framework: it will be the result of the capitalization of successful practices of the SPOKEs and will be built around a common shared nucleus while retaining space for personalization to accommodate individual SPOKEs specificities.

The framework will aim to offer the same value to all pre-accelerated ideas and let them access acceleration by following the same validation and development phases.; b) a Management & Educational Platform; it aims to develop and provide a reliable platform accessible by all SPOKES to efficiently (namely, to manage the Pre-Acceleration applications (Call for Ideas), to monitor and coordinate pre-acceleration programs, and to provide standardized educational modules and documentation); c) Scouting specialists; they will be identified by each SPOKE and will be responsible the first identification of innovative ideas, research project and early stage startups potentially interesting for the general objectives of the project. Since the project plans to perform the complete process two times, also the pre-acceleration phases will be performed two times.

- Sub Task CC1.2.1: Engagement and training of the Key Aligned Actors (10 Scouting specialists, one for each spoke - two for spoke 5, and pre-acceleration officer) of the pre-acceleration phase.

Responsible: UNIVE

Duration: months 9-40

- Sub Task CC1.2.2: Implementation of the Scouting Stage to attract entrepreneurs-to-be from the university's ecosystems and drive the research effort toward a proof-of-concept.

Responsible: UNIVE

Duration: months 10-23

- Sub Task CC1.2.3: Implementation of the online Entrepreneurial training through Management & Educational Platform to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.

Responsible: UNIVE

Duration: months 12-26

- Sub Task CC1.2.4: Open innovation activities. the objective of this task is to establish relationships with companies and other partners in order to facilitate the development of new projects, spinoffs and co-innovation activities between universities, startups and companies.

Responsible: UNIUD

Duration: months 9-40

*Task CC1.3 – Acceleration**Task Leader: Univr**Duration: M11 – M40*

The acceleration phase will follow the pre-acceleration phase. The goal of this centralized phase is to setup a model of research startup development capable to emerge as the reference point for innovation in (North-East) Italy, attracting venture and investors worldwide. The pre-acceleration phase will ensure a high quality overall; nonetheless, a centralized competition will select the participants of the previous pre-acceleration phases to be admitted to subsequent phases. To avoid any frictions among SPOKEs the selection of the startups to be admitted at any subsequent stage will be decided by the CCI committee taking into consideration of the advice given by a panel of sector experts and professional investors (i.e VCs). In month 15th (and in months 26 for the second round) the startups will be assisted in developing of proofs-of-concept and in exposing them to real market actors in their target sectors (pitch sessions). Then the selected startups will then participate to a 4 months acceleration program aimed at developing and validating innovative solutions. The acceleration program will follow the lean startup approach and will consists in ten two-weeks sprint sessions covering all the relevant issues to be addressed to successfully reach a seed-financing stage.

- Sub Task CC1.3.1: Development of the Key Standardized Elements (Acceleration Framework; Acceleration Physical Spaces) of the acceleration phase to provide a standardized educational model through the ecosystem.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 11-34

- Sub Task CC1.3.2: Engagement and coordination of the Key Actors (Acceleration officer, 2 StartUp Analysts) of the acceleration phase.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 14-40

- Sub Task CC1.3.3: Implementation of the Acceleration phase through Pitch Building & Pitch Session, Selection day, Onboarding and SCUM program. the objective of this phase is to bring the start-ups to validate the market and a scalable business model.

Responsible: UNIVR

Duration: months 15-32

Task CC1.4 Fundraising

Task Leader: Units

Duration: M15 - M40

In month 21, the first program shifts from the acceleration to the fundraising phase, leading successful startups to become scaleups. The 2-months VC-Invested Stage supports the investment ready scaleups to fulfill their financial needs and the 6-months Sustainable Stage will support scale-ups, part of the first program, towards their final Exit-IPO or Trade-Sale. The second round's firms will follow a similar process starting from the month 32.

- Sub Task CC1.4.1: Development of the Fundraising Network and Management. The task involves developing a fundraising network. This may include identifying potential VC capitals/Business Angels, creating fundraising strategies and maintaining the relationships with them. It may also involve using various tools and platforms to manage and track investments, as well as analyze and report on fundraising efforts.

Responsible: UNITS

Duration: months 15-40

- Sub Task CC1.4.2: Implementation of the VC-Invested Stage to support investment-ready scaleups fulfilling their financial needs. This task includes creating a comprehensive business plan that outlines the Start Up's goals, strategies, and financial projections. It should also involve identifying and approaching potential investors, including venture capital firms, and negotiating/structuring investment deals.

Responsible: UNITS

Duration: months 21-34

- Sub Task CC1.4.3: Design of the Sustainable Stage. The goal of this task is to provide skills, identify tools and evaluate market strategies to support scale-ups towards their final Exit-IPO or Trade-Sale.

Responsible: UNIPD

Duration: months 23-40

Deliverables

1 - Deliverable DCC1.1: Report on the Innovation Ecosystem's Key Elements

Responsible: Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE)

Date of delivery: March 2023

The report will give full disclosure on the organizational model of the Ecosystem by highlighting the collaborative network and the guidelines for operational transparency. The partners involved are then analyzed based on their support in each phase together with the global development strategy and the metrics necessary for understanding the future results of the cross-cutting activity. The report will also highlight the development results of the Key Standardized Elements on the pre-acceleration and the Key Centralized Elements on the acceleration. The report will also focus on the chronological transition from a decentralized yet coordinated SPOKES, with common standardized tools and guidelines, to a centralized acceleration hub.

2 - Deliverable DCC1.2: Report on the first pre-acceleration launches and the acceleration phase

Responsible: Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE)

Date of delivery: December 2023

The report will develop a first analysis on the results of the decentralized pre-acceleration framework and till the acceleration results of the first program.

3 - Deliverable DCC1.3: Report on pre-acceleration and acceleration results

Responsible: Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE)

Date of delivery: December 2024

The report will develop a complete analysis on the results of the decentralized pre-acceleration framework, as all the pre-acceleration data of all three programs are gathered. The report will also give further insights on the acceleration framework and on the preliminary results of the first fundraising program.

4 - Deliverable DCC1.4: Full Report on Innovation Ecosystem framework validation

Responsible: Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE)

Date of delivery: December 2025

The full report will analyze the data gathered by all three programs, from launch till their fundraising phase. To compare the results of the framework, the key elements are based on the success rate of ideas to reach an IPO or VC-Stage, on the criticalities and mitigation actions taken and, on the improvements made during the 40-month cross cutting activity. The full report will then be useful for validating the Innovation Ecosystem framework.

4 State of the Art

The following sections provide an up-to-date picture of the startup acceleration and spinoff activities existing in each spoke.

4.1 Spoke 1 - University of Bolzano

Entrepreneurial experience at UNIBZ – programs, activities, and facilities:

1. Activation of undergraduate and graduate courses in entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship (i.e. entrepreneurship with social impact) in the programmes offered by the Faculty of Economics and Management, Design and Art, Education, Computer Science and Science and Technology, Studium Generale.
2. Laurea Magistrale in Entrepreneurship and Innovation, since 2014, as a transformation of a previous Laurea Specialistica in Global Management and Markets, with a stream in Entrepreneurship and Innovation, activated in 2004. Students and alumni founded more than 15 new ventures in the last 8 years.
3. Observatory of Social Entrepreneurship and Social Innovation in South Tyrol, to tackle problems with social impact through an entrepreneurial approach. Training, education, study, support to the entrepreneurial ecosystem.
4. Bitz- the unibz fablab, opened in 2018 to support prototyping and entrepreneurial mindset. This facility is open to unibz students, researchers, as well as to the citizens.

Support to the diffusion of entrepreneurial ecosystem in South Tyrol activities:

- Organizations and participation in hackathons and innovation challenges both at local and international level, such as Startup Weekend, EUvsVirus, Student & Company Sprint Weekend.
- Design and implementation of programmes open to citizens to support the development of new ventures with social impact: SIAA Lab (ITA-A Interreg project); Coopmindset for Entrepreneurial Cooperatives, by OISIS.
- Activities and projects to increase public engagement towards Entrepreneurship, such as: Global Entrepreneurship Week, Long Night of Research, Max Talks, Arduino Day, Genuino Day, etc.

Consulting and support to enhance the entrepreneurial ecosystem:

- Support to implementation of business model competitions organized by other institutions, such as NOI Tech (Startup Competition IDM, Adventure X, Vertical Hackathon, etc.), Alperia, (Startup Factory), Cassa di Risparmio di Bolzano (Radius), MIND Meran, etc.
- Support to the design and the implementation of the program to support the development of startups (Bando di capitalizzazione) by the Dept. of Innovation and Research, Province of BZ. Design and implementation of innovation challenges, such as Institutional cooperation activated through initiative to support entrepreneurship: NOI Tech, tba-network, Assoimprenditori.

4.2 Spoke 2 - University of Trento

1 School of Innovation. The School of Innovation (SOI) is an interdepartmental structure of the University of Trento that offers interdisciplinary and applied education on innovation and entrepreneurship. It was launched in 2016 as a strategic project to enrich the traditional university didactic offer and respond to the emerging needs of students and lifelong learners. SOI courses equip learners with tools and skills to develop and promote innovation processes in different sectors, such as technical, scientific, social and humanistic. SOI also builds on the experience of CLab Trento, the centre to develop an entrepreneurial mindset and passion for innovation. SOI is hosted in the Clab Trento interdisciplinary laboratories, which foster the entrepreneurial vision of innovation and its implementation through challenge-based learning opportunities. SOI aims to create a network of experts, students, professionals and organizations that can collaborate and exchange insights and perspectives on innovation.

2 CLab Trento. Clab Trento is the physical space and interdisciplinary laboratory of the University of Trento, managed in strategic partnership with Hub Innovazione Trentino, which hosts all the activities referring to the School of Innovation brand. Since 2017, CLab Trento has become part of the CLab Network, the network of CLabs in Italian universities.

3 Business Design. In 2022, the School of Innovation at the University of Trento, in collaboration with the HIT Foundation, launched the second edition of Business Design. This course aims to guide participants from outside the academic environment in the design of innovative products and services. The course aims to develop basic entrepreneurship skills in the participants. By combining traditional elements of market analysis and business strategy with methodologies such as design thinking and human-centered design, the course allows you to test the key hypotheses underlying the business model before launching the innovative product or service in the market, thus reducing the risk of failure.

Teams are accompanied by faculty and experts from the world of entrepreneurship and innovation and have access to a dedicated mentorship program. With their support, participants can begin shaping the contours of their entrepreneurial initiative.

4 StartUp Lab. The Start-Up Lab (SUL) is an interdisciplinary practical course running once a year for 4 months on innovation and entrepreneurship (I&E) and is one of the main pillars of the CLab at the University of Trento. SUL offers an innovative learning experience focused on customer-centered creativity, idea generation, optimization, and presentation of business ideas. It is primarily an idea generation lab built around the CPS (Customer Problem Solution) and lean startup principles and aims to develop innovative products/services that can potentially transform into a start-up. Students are constantly guided by professionals and entrepreneurs and present in front of an international jury during the SUL Demoday.

5 Enactus. Enactus is a global non-profit organization that brings together students, entrepreneurs, academics and business leaders who see business as a way to address social problems. Enactus aims to empower students to develop social entrepreneurship projects that can create positive impact on their communities and the world. Enactus operates in 36 countries and involves 72,000 students who work under the guidance and collaboration of experts to identify and solve the most complex issues in their local contexts. Enactus Trento is one of the teams that represents Italy in the Enactus network. It was founded in 2017 and participated in the World Cup 2017 in London.

It currently consists of 11 members with different academic backgrounds. Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT) is a foundation that supports the development and growth of the territory through sustainable innovation and the valorization of research results. It is an instrumental entity of the Autonomous Province of Trento and a research and knowledge dissemination organization according to the European Union regulations. HIT acts as a bridge between the excellence of scientific and technological research of its founders (University of Trento, Bruno Kessler Foundation, Edmund Mach Foundation, Trentino Sviluppo) and the opportunities and demands of innovation in the market. HIT is involved in activities such as open innovation, technology transfer, new entrepreneurship, events and training, doctoral education, and digital innovation hub.

HIT is also a partner of five KICs (Knowledge and Innovation Communities) of the European Institute of Technology and eight national technological clusters. HIT plays a key role in the technology transfer and innovation activities of the University of Trento.

6 Trentino Startup Valley. Trentino Startup Valley is a startup creation support programme for aspiring entrepreneurs who want to transform their innovative ideas into successful businesses. The programme is promoted by Trentino Sviluppo (the local development agency whose mission is to support companies' growth) and Fondazione HIT - Hub Innovazione Trentino (whose mission is to foster the startup creation from research). The programme supports innovative ideas who want to open their business in Trentino and deep-tech startups created from research partners in Trentino, such as the University of Trento, Fondazione Bruno Kessler and Fondazione Mach. The programme consists of two phases: Bootstrap and Validation, for a total duration of 12 months. During these phases, the participants receive personalised coaching, economic support, coworking spaces, access to specialized consultants, investors and business angels. At the end of each phase, there are demo days where the startups pitch their projects to a jury and a public audience with the possibility of receiving funding.

4.3 Spoke 3 - University of Udine

Entrepreneurial experience at UNIUD - programs, activities, and facilities: UNIUD Structures and Offices dealing with Technology Transfer (TT), Startups (SU), Spinoffs (SO) and contacts with enterprises (CE).

Technology Transfer Office and Placement TTO&P

TTO&P is responsible for supporting and developing the University innovative activity. The TTO&P's mission is to promote the transfer of skills, knowledge and technologies from inventors, innovators and entrepreneurs to the wider community.

TTO&P operates in the following fields:

- Activities creating awareness, education and publicity (to promote more effective interaction with industries, to match up industry needs with University capacities).
- University-industry collaboration (acting as interface between University and industry by transmitting innovative knowledge from research to outside organization or by searching inside the University for the research requests of companies).
- Supporting start up and spin off companies (by assisting academics during the process of establishing start up companies and to promote entrepreneurial culture between students).

Since 2002, 46 companies have been set up at the University of Udine, of which 32 are still active. The activity area of these companies is included in the fields of mathematics and computer sciences (22%), agricultural and food sciences (28%), engineering (28%) and medical sciences (13%), economics, statistics and law (7%) and chemical sciences, civil engineering, environment and architecture (2%).

According to the regulation updated in 2016, a society can be recognized as spin off (if the University is a shareholder of the company) or start up (if the university is not a shareholder of the company) only for a period of 5 years. In 2022 there are active 6 spin offs and 5 startups. TTO&P includes now 2 structures: Career Center (since 2016) and Punto Impresa (since 2018).

Punto Impresa (PI)

PI is a structure that was created in 2018, with the aim of enhancing the dialogue between industrial and academic communities, and to contribute to the civil, cultural, social and economic development of the territory. PI is located within the Technology Transfer and Placement Office and the University Research Services Area.

PI deals with the following activities:

- informing, guiding and accompanying companies and researchers in building virtuous relationships that lead to the practical application and development of new knowledge;
- guiding companies in the development of personalized training plans;
- offering support to companies concerning placement and recruitment activities.

These activities are carried out by organizing and managing publications, digital tools and events, in particular:

1. A monthly Newsletter indicating events and opportunities for keeping contacts with companies, promoting announcements, tenders and initiatives of UNIUD for business;
2. Live streaming events, and implementation of communication via social networks;
3. Implementation of Customer Relationship Management Softwares aimed at improving the knowledge of UNIUD relationships with enterprises, concerning trainees, placement and collaboration, as well as for mapping contracts and the participation of companies to Projects;
4. Events and round tables: 13 events (online or in presence) organized in 2022;
5. Organization of "Calls for enterprises", with the aim to propose/suggest to companies initiatives for business to be implemented jointly (10 calls published in 2022);
6. Networking. PI participates and/or maintains relationships with various entities, including Fondazione Friuli, Confindustria, Confartigianato, Agrifood FVG, Fondazione CRUI, Regione Autonoma Friuli Venezia Giulia, SMOACT Competence Center, ENACTUS;
7. One-to-One assistance to companies, for suggesting to firms suitable collaboration strategies with UNIUD aimed at resolving practical problems or implementing joint R&D or training projects;
8. Initiatives for the development of business culture, with the purpose of training and assisting young entrepreneurs in the development of new ideas or Startups.

Other UNIUD figures and structures:

- in addition and in synergy with PI, other figures operate in this area, such as the Delegate of the Rector for Placement, Alumni and Relations with Enterprises, the Delegate of the Rector for the “Third Mission”, the Delegate for Technology Transfer and the Spin-Off Technical Committee.

4.4 Spoke 4 - University of IUAV

Entrepreneurial experience at IUAV – programs, activities, and facilities:

- IUAV's approach is initially educational, with the goal of helping aspiring entrepreneurs and individuals interested in launching a business understand what it entails.
- StartUp School: A startup school is organized, with open meetings for everyone to attend. Course attendance allows students to earn university credits and LinkedIn badges.
- 2. The second initiative focuses on matching, aimed at increasing mutual contamination and collaboration. This is achieved through two initiatives: Call to action and Thematic tables.

Once a year, an official call for proposals called Start Hub is organized. To participate, certain requirements must be met: a team of at least three members, with one member affiliated with IUAV.

Additionally, the team should already have an identified project. Normally, 12 projects are selected, and each is assigned a mentor. Three appointments on a specific theme are scheduled. Subsequently, an intensive laboratory is organized, with accommodation provided. The mornings consist of training sessions, while group work takes place in the afternoons.

The emphasis is particularly on structuring a presentation useful for a pitch. A month after the intensive laboratory, a plenary presentation is organized, involving the Rector and various authorities. On this occasion, it is also necessary to present a prototype. The top 5 initiatives are awarded a cash prize.

4.5 Spoke 5 - University of Padova

Entrepreneurial experience at UNIPD – programs, activities, and facilities:

1 Third Mission Sector – provides initial consultancy to those who intend to start a university spin-off startup and guides them through all the stages of establishment or recognition of the spin-off.

2 Start Cube (Galileo Incubator) is the university incubator of Padua, a structure created to facilitate the birth of new businesses through a joint project between the University of Padua and the Cassa di Risparmio Foundation of Padua and Rovigo. Since 2016, it has been acquired as a branch of the company by Galileo Visionary District, the scientific and technological park of Padua, with the aim of expanding support for startups and spin-offs. Dedicated to newly established or in-progress companies, the Start Cube incubator provides support and consultancy services at favorable conditions, aiming to reduce the burdens associated with starting a business and increase awareness among future entrepreneurs.

3 Event Organization: Events are organized among startups, spin-offs, and local entrepreneurship.

4 Unismart - University of Padua Foundation is the foundation of the university created to promote technology transfer and post-graduate education. Unismart serves as a meeting point between academic excellence, the business world, and private and public stakeholders, with the aim of enhancing university resources and expertise by proactively and effectively managing short and long-term collaborations involving all faculty, researchers, students, staff, and partners of its Open Innovation Community. Unismart valorizes patents, activates and manages research and innovation consultancy projects, provides training activities through Masters programs, corporate courses, and lifelong learning, promotes collaborative European projects, and engages in activities with students and PhD candidates. The Unismart Community is the ecosystem that embodies the paradigm of open innovation. Multinational corporations, SMEs, startups, banks, trade associations, municipalities, and organizations from diverse markets engage in dialogue with each other and with the university, challenging themselves through discussion and generating value through numerous initiatives. Unismart acts as a bridge between scientists and entrepreneurs or managers, providing concrete solutions to the needs of private and public organizations interested in embarking on innovation journeys.

5 Netval – Promotion and valorization of research aimed at sharing and strengthening the skills of Italian universities and research institutions in research valorization, knowledge transfer, and intellectual property protection, involving the business world.

6 Elis - Elis promotes collaboration among all entities contributing to the country's economic development. Meeting their needs with innovation projects is the specific task of ELIS Innovation Hub. It carries out consulting projects involving universities, research centers, and startups, facilitating the encounter between their innovative potential and the needs of the productive world. It builds multidisciplinary working groups designed around customer needs, combining junior profiles with experienced professionals. The consulting activities of ELIS Innovation Hub offer all involved partners the opportunity to participate in the creation of the common good generated by innovation and development, improving products and services, streamlining business and production processes, and experimenting with and facilitating the adoption of advanced digital technologies.

7 Open Italy Program (Elis) is the program for open and collaborative innovation for companies, startups, and innovation enablers. The program provides an opportunity for large companies and innovative entities to work together to develop new solutions, fostering a culture of open innovation.

4.6 Spoke 6 - University of Venezia Ca' Foscari

Entrepreneurial experience at UNIVE - programs, activities, and facilities:

1 PlnK - Promotion of Innovation and Know-how is the portal of Ca' Foscari University of Venice dedicated to startups, aiming to promote the transfer of technological knowledge between university research and the local territory. Through PlnK, collaboration between the university and entrepreneurship takes shape to enhance the results of research and foster innovation and development in the productive system. At the end of 2022, the university regulations were renewed, unifying the management of spin-offs and patents. The main activity of PlnK concerns the accreditation of university spin-offs, which have the characteristics of innovative startups and involve services and products originating from university research. The support offered includes the accreditation process (i.e., verification of the prerequisites and approval by the department and senate/board of directors) and the preparation of business plans. The accreditation of spin-offs lasts for 5 years, during which various services are provided: spaces, laboratories, use of trademarks, patent consultancy, and events. Recently, PlnK has also opened up to the possibility of student startups, with similar conditions as mentioned above, although there are no cases yet. At the end of the 5-year period, spin-offs enter an ecosystem of affiliated entities called "Mosaico."

2 Mosaico Ecosystem - After the initial 5 years of spin-off, there is a new path called the Innovation Ecosystem - Mosaico Ecosystem, which aims to integrate awareness and training courses for PhD students, researchers, and professors focused on entrepreneurship.

3 Ca' Foscari Contamination Lab (CLab) consists of its own laboratories lasting 6-8 weeks, with the goal of guiding university students and graduates from different disciplinary backgrounds in the process of developing original projects that tackle real challenges and problems. The focus is on leveraging their creativity using innovative methodologies such as Design Thinking and the Business Model Canvas.

4 Enactus organizes an annual competition for entrepreneurial projects aligned with the goals of the 2030 Agenda, specifically targeting university students.

5 Start Up Cup Veneto was a business plan competition organized by the universities of Verona, Padua, and IUAV Venice until 2021.

6 Netval: The university is part of the NetVal network, which promotes the valorization of research results through training and networking activities.

7 Ca' Foscari is among the promoters of VeniSIA, an innovation accelerator focused on sustainability, based in Venice. It is oriented towards the development of entrepreneurial ideas and technological solutions capable of addressing climate change and other environmental challenges. VeniSIA attracts institutions, companies, and individuals who share the belief that this is the perfect context to provide ideas and solutions for sustainable development challenges within the fragile and unique environmental ecosystem of Venice, while also being scalable for the benefit of the entire planet. The ultimate goal of VeniSIA is not just to create an accelerator in Venice but to make Venice itself an accelerator.

4.7 Spoke 7 - University of Verona

Entrepreneurial experience at UNIVR – programs, activities, and facilities:

1 Start Up Cup Veneto is a business plan competition organized by the universities of Verona, Padua, and IUAV Venice.

2 Contamination Lab Verona is an interdisciplinary and transversal path aimed at students, utilizing non-traditional teaching methods with training modules dedicated to innovation and entrepreneurial culture.

3 T2i: The university has entered into an agreement with t2i, a certified incubator of the Veneto Region, which supports our professors and researchers in the establishment of spin-offs through a convention. Duration: year-round.

4 Enactus organizes an annual competition for entrepreneurial projects aligned with the goals of the 2030 Agenda, dedicated to university students.

5 Scuola di Autoimprenditoria organized by ESU Verona consists of two days focused on the basic elements of creating a new business, targeting students.

6 Investiamo sul futuro is a program on the local television network TeleArena dedicated to Verona's startups. It provides general information about university spin-offs, the Chamber of Commerce's spin-offs, and T2i.

7 In 2021, the university collaborated in organizing an event dedicated to startups during the Future Arena of the Festival Del Futuro, a networking format dedicated to the world of innovation. Some university spin-offs presented pitches to compete for prizes.

8 Meetings/seminars with PhD students on the topic of entrepreneurship and industrial property protection.

9 Premio IMSA (Italian Master Startup Award) was hosted in 2020.

10 PNI Cube: Univr is a member of the association of university incubators that organizes the National Innovation Award every year, which was hosted in Verona in 2018.

4.8 Spoke 8 - University of Trieste

Entrepreneurial experience at **Polo Alto Adriatico** - programs, activities, and facilities:

- Polo Alto Adriatico (PAA) is a Technology park located in Pordenone. Since its foundation, in 2002, it has been involved in technology transfer and entrepreneurial development. The services offered include:

1 Consultancy services for businesses, especially in the field of digital transformation and industry 4.0.

2 Assistance in launching and developing startups, with physical incubation, pre-acceleration and acceleration services.

The pre-acceleration activity is based on an internally developed tool for assessing the potential of the business idea (economic, technological and market feasibility), followed by qualitative assessment meetings with industry experts. The package of services offered is completed by assistance for the protection of intellectual property, assistance in defining the business model, defining corporate governance, and preparing the business plan. Finally, PAA supports companies in their search for financing, both subsidized and on the market, thanks to contact with a network of business angels, VCs and PEs. There are currently over 40 incubated companies

4.9 Spoke 9 - SISSA

Entrepreneurial experience at SISSA - programs, activities, and facilities

At SISSA, Technology and Knowledge Transfer is a crucial and strategic activity within the so called Academic Third Mission. Concrete and structured actions have been taken in order to systemically promote innovation, valorize internal research and talents, and improve the impact of the School on society and on the productive and economic ecosystem.

These have culminated with the establishment of the Valorisation and Innovation Office, which main objective is to manage and promote all the processes, including the constitution of start-ups, that can create value from the valorization of internal assets (competencies, know-how, technologies, etc.), as well as to continuously motivate the community of SISSA to create a virtuous contamination of ideas with societal and economic stakeholders.

In particular, the Valorisation and Innovation Office is active in:

- 1.promoting the innovative activity and entrepreneurial approach of students as well as that of senior researchers;
- 2.increasing the structured cooperation at all levels with SMEs, Companies, Investors, Governmental Agencies, etc., including public and private incubators and accelerators specifically focused on new ventures creations (AREA Science Park, BIC Incubator, Bio4Dreams, Sofinnova, Venture Factory, 360 Capital, TerraLab Venture Capital, etc.);
- 3.improving the knowledge valorization and its impact through cross fertilization initiatives;
- 4.guaranteeing the legal compliance and negotiating the best conditions for all the agreements needed to implement the above-mentioned activities;
- 5.identifying, assessing, protecting and licensing internal Intellectual Property;
- 6.internal scouting and networking with industry, venture capital and industrial experts in order to identify, protect and evaluate commercial exploitation of the research results internally conceived (also thorough new ventures creation).

As a result of these activities and of the investments made by the Direction in the last years:

- 1.SISSA has interacted and collaborated for innovation purposes with **50+ companies** in the last 3 years;
- 2.a total amount of **680.000,00+ Euro** of commercial (contract research and IP licensing) agreements have been signed in 2022;
- 3.**8 start-ups** were founded and **14 patent** families were extended at international level, **9 of which are commercialized** (licensed and under exclusive option rights).

SISSA is one of the university partners of the national competence centre for Industry 4.0 (SMACT) in the fields of Data Science, Artificial Intelligence and Digital Twin. There are collaborations with Università degli Studi di Trieste and Università degli Studi di Udine through Unity FVG, which allows for the grouping and standardization of procedures in a coordinated manner for NDAs, patents, etc. Together with Università degli Studi di Trieste, Università degli Studi di Udine, ICTP Centro Internazionale di Fisica Teorica, MIB Trieste School of Management and Assicurazioni Generali S.p.A., SISSA has established the Interuniversity Center in data science and artificial intelligence "DS-AI INSTITUTE".

The Valorisation and Innovation Office has put in place several initiatives aimed at promoting the **talent development of PhD students** in the field of **industrial innovation and entrepreneurship**. The office developed customized initiatives to engage and to convey a new approach. Given the specificities deriving from its own special order, international nature and the almost exclusive focus on third-level advanced training, SISSA has focused its offer on “tailored made” actions, designed on the basis of the specific needs of students, such as:

1. PhD for INNOVATION (as well as the past editions called “PHD4PMI”) to connect the world of industry with SISSA talents by involving them in industrial challenges through training-by doing;
2. specific seminars, also online, with important speakers in the field (including investors and venture capitalists linked to the valorization of research);
3. the enhancement of the skills (both technical and soft) and the know-how, also through a service of coaching one-to-one (CV review, interviews preparation, personal branding, entrepreneurship attitude development);
4. the mentoring service with SISSA’s Alumni and collaboration with the SISSA’s Alumni Association;
5. two Entrepreneurship Summer Schools;
6. Job Fairs and placement/recruiting days.

As regards the enhancement of the entrepreneurship approach, it is worth to mention the organization of a two-week advanced specialist training course based on the ‘MARS42 Summer Entrepreneurship School’ held in English-speaking countries.

This initiative was organised together with The Doers/Accelerator42, a leading Italian enterprise specialised in accelerator programmes for start-ups and spin-offs. Together with Università degli Studi di Trieste and Università degli Studi di Udine, SISSA has organised the ‘Start Cup FVG’. This initiative ran a competition for the most original business plans for enterprises and start-ups. JoTTO project has been initiated with IMT, GSSI, IUSS, Scuola Normale Superiore and Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, although it is not directly related to the acceleration theme.

	UNIBZ	UNITN	UNIUD	IUAV	UNIPD	UNIVE	UNivr	PAA	SISSA
Preacceleration	Active faculty scouting					✓			✓
	Active student scouting								✓
Acceleration	Entrepreneurial training			✓		✓			
	Development of acceleration methodologies			✓	✓	✓		✓	
	Pitch building activities				✓	✓		✓	
Funding	Scrum program				✓	✓		✓	
	Network management for Startup		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Openinnovation	Support for VC Pitch					✓		✓	
	Support for participation in call for proposals	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
	Regular contacts with companies	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Legal	Joint activities implementation				✓	✓		✓	✓
	Presence of stable structures for interaction	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓
Eventi	Legal advice on NDAs				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Contractual advice			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Incubation	Company and governance consultancy				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Patent, trademark, etc. consultancy			✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Shared services	Startup community events		✓			✓	✓		
	Startup contests		✓			✓	✓		
Mentoring	Startup contests		✓			✓	✓		
	Hosting		✓			✓	✓		
Shared services	Hosting		✓			✓	✓		
	Shared services		✓			✓	✓		

Table 1. Spokes activities

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